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Kinetics and Mechanism of Oxidation of some Primary Alcohols by *N*-Bromobenzamide

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REPORTS are available in literature on the mechanism of oxidation by chloramine-T¹, chloramine-B², *N*-bromosuccinimide³ and other haloamides, however, no information is available about the modes of the redox reactions of *N*-bromobenzamide (NBB). The different mechanistic pathways reported for the structurally related *N*-haloamides⁴⁻⁷ prompted us to undertake this investigation.

Experimental

Alcohols (B.D.H., A.R. and S.M., G.R.) were purified by the reported method⁸. Acetic acid was distilled over chromic acid before use. Perchloric acid was used as a source of hydrogen ions. All other chemicals used were of B.D.H., A.R. or S.M., G.R. quality. The reaction vessels were coated with black paint to exclude any photochemical effect.

Kinetic measurements: The reactions were carried out under pseudo-first order conditions by keeping a large excess of alcohol over NBB. The temperature was kept constant within $\pm 0.1^\circ$. The solvent used was 1 : 1 (v/v) acetic acid—water, unless mentioned otherwise. The reactions were followed iodometrically for over 70% of the reaction. The pseudo-first order rate constants (K_1) were computed from the plot of $\log [NBB]$ against time. Dupli-

cate kinetic runs indicate that the reaction rate constants were reproducible within $\pm 4.0\%$. Preliminary experiments showed that the reaction is not sensitive to ionic strength hence no attempt was made to keep it constant.

Results

When the alcohol is in excess, the first order plots show that the reaction is composed of two successive steps; the initial slow reaction followed by a fast reaction. Such observations were made in the oxidation of alcohols by *N*-bromosuccinimide⁴⁻⁶. The second faster reaction is attributed to either the oxidation of alcohols by bromine or to the reaction of bromine with carbonyl product⁴. This was suppressed by the addition of 0.005 *M* mercuric acetate.

Dependence of rate on oxidant concentration: The time order of the reaction is found to be one with respect to oxidant as evidenced by the constancy of the first order rate constants at different times. Concentration order of the reaction with respect to oxidant is also one, as evidenced by the independency of the rate constant on the initial concentration of the oxidant. Results obtained are summarised in Table 1.

TABLE 1

[Substrate] = 1.0 mol dm⁻³, [Hg(OAc)₂] = 5.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³,
[HOAc] = 50% (v/v), [HClO₄] = 0.5 mol dm⁻³, Temp. = 323 K

Sl. no.	[NBB] × 10 ³ mol dm ⁻³	$k_1 \times 10^3$, min ⁻¹	
		Ethanol	Propan-1-ol
1.	2.50	1.52	2.78
2.	3.75	1.58	2.82
3.	5.00	1.68	2.80
4.	6.25	1.70	2.78
5.	7.50	1.62	2.76
6.	8.75	1.58	2.84

Dependence of rate on substrate concentration: The rate constants at different initial concentrations of the substrate have been obtained. The plots of pseudo-first order rate constants against substrate concentration exhibit linearity for the given range of substrate concentrations. The plot of $\log k$ vs $\log [C]$ gives a slope value of unity. This

TABLE 2

[NBB] = 5.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, [HClO₄] = 0.5 mol dm⁻³,
HOAc = 50% (v/v), [Hg(OAc)₂] = 5.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³,
Temp. 323 K

Sl. no.	[Substrate] mol dm ⁻³	$k_1 \times 10^3$	
		Ethanol	Propan-1-ol
1.	0.50	0.82	1.41
2.	0.75	1.21	2.06
3.	1.00	1.68	2.80
4.	1.25	2.02	3.48
5.	1.50	2.40	4.21
6.	2.00	3.20	5.59

suggests that the order with respect to substrate is one. The results are summarised in Table 2.

Dependence of rate on perchloric acid concentration: It has been found that the reaction rate increases with increasing the concentration of perchloric acid. Interestingly, the order with respect to perchloric acid varies with the change in perchloric acid concentration. It was found to be first order above approximately 0.5 M and fractional order below 0.5 M of perchloric acid concentration (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. A plot $\log k$ vs $\log c$; variation of HClO_4 : ($\square$) propan-1-ol, and ($\circ$) ethanol.

Effect of added benzamide: It has been found that the reaction rate decreases due to the addition of benzamide. The results are presented in Table 3.

TABLE 3

[Propan-1-ol] = 1 mol dm^{-3} , [NBB] = 5.0×10^{-3} mol dm^{-3} ,
HOAc = 50% (v/v), [Hg(OAc)₂] = 5.0×10^{-3} mol dm^{-3} ,
[HClO₄] = 1 mol dm^{-3} , Temp. = 323 K

Sl. no.	[Benzamide] $\times 10^3$	$k_1 \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$
1.	00.0	4.35
2.	01.0	3.71
3.	02.0	3.38
4.	05.0	3.29
5.	08.0	2.50
6.	10.0	1.92

Effect of bromide ion: It has been found that the reaction rate is enhanced by the initial addition of potassium bromide. The results are summarised in Table 4.

TABLE 4

[Propan-1-ol] = 1 mol dm^{-3} , [NBB] = 5.0×10^{-3} mol dm^{-3} ,
HOAc = 50% (v/v), [Hg(OAc)₂] = 5.0×10^{-3} mol dm^{-3} ,
[HClO₄] = 1 mol dm^{-3} , Temp. = 323 K

Sl. no.	[KBr] $\times 10^{-3}$	$k_1 \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$
1.	00	4.35
2.	01	4.47
3.	02	4.80
4.	04	5.00
5.	06	5.23
6.	08	6.74
7.	10	11.81

Temperature variation and activation parameters: The reaction was studied at various temperatures to evaluate activation parameters. The data of activation parameters are given in the Tables 5 and 6.

TABLE 5

[Substrate] = 1 mol dm^{-3} , [NBB] = 5.0×10^{-3} mol dm^{-3} ,
HOAc = 50% (v/v), [Hg(OAc)₂] = 5.0×10^{-3} mol dm^{-3} ,
[HClO₄] = 1 mol dm^{-3}

Sl. no.	Temp. K	$k_1 \times 10^3, \text{ min}^{-1}$	
		Ethanol	Propan-1-ol
1.	313	1.12	1.44
2.	318	1.96	2.48
3.	323	3.10	4.35
4.	328	5.69	7.57

TABLE 6

[Substrate] = 1 mol dm^{-3} , [NBB] = 5.0×10^{-3} mol dm^{-3} ,
HOAc = 50% (v/v), [Hg(OAc)₂] = 5.0×10^{-3} mol dm^{-3} ,
[HClO₄] = 1 mol dm^{-3}

Substrate	$\Delta E^\ddagger$ kJ mol^{-1}	$\Delta K^\ddagger$ k ¹ mol^{-1}	PZ dm ³ mol^{-1} min	$\Delta S^\ddagger$ JK ⁻¹ mol^{-1}
Ethanol	92.4	89.8	2.94×10^{12}	-6.75
Propan-1-ol	96.8	94.2	1.96×10^{12}	+9.02

Stoichiometry of the reaction: Stoichiometry of the reaction was also studied. It was observed that one mole of alcohol gets oxidised by one mole of the oxidant,

Discussion

The retardation of the rate of oxidation with added benzamide suggests that pre-equilibrium step involves a process in which benzamide is one of the products (equation 2). The increase in the rate of oxidation with acidity points out the protonation of HOBr to give a cationic bromide species—a stronger electrophile and oxidant (equation 3). The reaction proceeds, albeit slowly, even in absence of perchloric acid. From this observation, it is likely that in the absence of added mineral acid the oxidising species is HOBr. The protonation may, however, precede hydrolysis of $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CONHBr}$, and it is not possible to distinguish kinetically between the reactions (2) and (3) from (4) and (5). A plot of $\log k_1$ against the inverse of dielectric constant of acetic acid—water mixture is linear with positive slope. This according to Amis⁹, indicates a positive ion-dipole reaction. This is in accordance with our suggestion that (H_2OBr^+) is active oxidising species. In consonance with the results obtained by us, the following reaction scheme may be suggested for the oxidation of primary alcohols with NBB.

or alternate path.

The formation of hypobromite ester ($R-CH_2-O-Br$) in the rate determining step (as suggested by Banerji and Negi¹⁰) may be excluded considering the values of entropy of activation. Hence, the proposed reaction mechanism for the oxidation of primary alcohol with NBB is very consistent with the experimental findings.

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Synthesis of Steroidal Oxazolidinone

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OXAZOLIDINONE derivatives have been proved to possess a variety of biological activities, such as antidepressant¹, antibacterial², fungicidal^{3,4}, herbicidal⁵, analgesic⁶, antiinflammatory¹, muscle-relaxant^{1,7} and anticonvulsant^{7,8}. These physiological properties prompted us to undertake the synthetic studies of steroidal oxazolidinones. For this objective, 3 α ,4 α -epoxy-6-nitrocholest-5-ene (1)⁹ was used

as the starting material. When the epoxide (1) was treated with phenylisocyanate in *N,N*-dimethylformamide, the *trans*-dihydroxy compound (2) and the desired oxazolidinone (3) were obtained. The structures of these products were established from chemical analysis and spectral data. The epoxide (1) on treatment with acrylamide under similar reaction conditions also provided the same hydroxy compound (2) and oxazolidinone (3).

Experimental

All melting points were determined on a Kofler's block apparatus and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Pye-Unicam sp 3-100 spectrophotometer. Nmr spectra ($CDCl_3$) were run on a Varian A-60D instrument using TMS as internal standard. Light petroleum refers to the fraction b p 60–80°.

Reaction of 3 α ,4 α -epoxy-6-nitrocholest-5-ene (1) with phenylisocyanate- $AlCl_3$: 3 α ,4 α -Epoxy-6-nitrocholest-5-ene⁹ (1; 1.5 g) in *N,N*-dimethylformamide (25 ml) was refluxed with phenylisocyanate (1 ml) ($AlCl_3$ added as catalyst) for 20 min. After the completion of the reaction, it was worked up in ether. The ethereal solution was washed with water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Evaporation of the solvent provided an oil which was chromatographed over a column of silica gel (30g). Elution with petroleum-ether (8:1) provided a solid compound 2, recrystallised from light petroleum, (300 mg), m.p. 120° (Found: C, 72.48; H, 10.06; N, 3.18. $C_{27}H_{45}NO_4$ requires: C, 72.48; H, 10.06; N, 3.13%); ν_{max} 3410 (OH), 1640 (C=C), 1530 and 1370 cm^{-1} (C-NO₂); δ 4.45 (1H, d, J 4Hz, C4- α H), 4.03 (1H, mc, $W_{1/2}$ 7Hz, C3- β H), 2.65 (OH), 1.28 (C10-CH₃), 0.68 (C13-CH₃), 0.92 and 0.82 (other angular methyl protons).

Further elution with light petroleum-ether (4:1) yielded 3, recrystallised from light petroleum (400 mg) m.p. 137° (Found: C, 71.09; H, 9.39; N, 5.88; $C_{28}H_{44}N_2O_4$ requires: C, 71.18; H, 9.32; N, 5.89%); ν_{max} 3420 br (NH) 1725 (oxazolidinone moiety), 1650 (C=C), 1525 and 1365 cm^{-1} (C-NO₂). δ 8.01 (1H, s, NH, exchangeable with D_2O), 5.48 (1H, d, J 3Hz C4- β H), 3.98 (1H, mc, $W_{1/2}$ 7Hz, C3- β H), 1.20 (C10-CH₃), 0.66 (C13-CH₃), 0.88 and 0.78 (remaining methyl protons).

Reaction of 3 α ,4 α -epoxy-6-nitrocholest-5-ene (1) with acrylamide- $AlCl_3$: 3 α ,4 α -epoxy-6-nitrocholest-5-ene⁹ (1; 1.5 g) in *N,N*-dimethylformamide (25 ml)